

On some contact-induced changes in Pomak and the role of Greek

Evangelia Thomadaki, Christina Markou
Democritus University of Thrace
ethomada@bscc.duth.gr, cmarkou@bscc.duth.gr

The present study aims at contributing to the discussion on language contact between different languages in the Balkans, focusing on the relationship between Pomak and Greek mainly. Due to the complex historical and socio-political conditions that defined the situation of Pomak communities in Greek Thrace (Voss 2007, Tsibiridou 2000), the south-Slavic local varieties used as native language by the speakers of these communities are exposed to influence from dominant Turkish and Greek (Adamou 2010, 2012) and have until recently been primarily employed in oral communication (Ioannidou & Voss 2001, Manova 2011).

This study presents some findings concerning the manner and extent of contact-induced borrowings from Greek and Turkish into Pomak, as documented in various text types produced by Greek Pomak speakers. According to Adamou (2010) Pomak has borrowed from Turkish (although less extensively than Greek Romani in Thrace). The influence of Greek is different in nature, being both more limited and recent, but as we intend to show it may affect the speech of Pomak speakers not only at the level of isolated lexical loans but also at a structural level, since it can be detected in calque expressions such as:

- (1) *ša 'zemeš da ot'voriš i 'dvæne ko'ri...*
'(lit.) you get round to rolling out two thin phyllo pastry sheets',
(compare: MGr. *perno na anikso filo* '(lit.) get round to **rolling out thin phyllo pastry** sheets')
- (2) *Za jen'no gu'dina 'votre* (lit.) 'in a year within'
(comp. Gr. *mesa se ena xrono* 'within a year')

Since usage of such elements depends on factors defining the communicative situation (such as the perceived linguistic orientation of the participant, the available vocabulary resources, type of text produced), different text types will be compared in order to show these tendencies.

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